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The prevalence of violence among a group of married women attending two teaching hospitals in Baghdad

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Abstract

Background: Violence is an important public health problem world wide. Domestic violence against women is particularly concerning as its generally perpetrated within relationships that are supposed to involve care and protection is a much more serious problem than violence perpetrated by strangers. **The aim of this study** is to assess the prevalence of violence against women, and studying possible risk factors that may be associated with this.

Patients and methods: From March 2006 to August 2006, 323 Arabian women 265 married (82%), 34 widows (10.5%), 24 divorced (7.4%) were observed at Al-Kadhimiya and Al-Kindy teaching hospitals and interviewed to determine their exposure to violence. Their age ranged from 18 to 70 years (Mean age 39 years). They were interviewed regardless whether they were attending as a patients or not.

Results: Domestic violence (DV) by husband was reported in 186 women (57.6 %) for at least one incident and 117 women (44%) for continuous or current violence. Violence not by husband was reported in 67 women (20.7%) as past experience.

While 16 women (5%) with continued exposure to violence. Psychological violence was the major type of DV by husband occurring in 185 women (57.3%), followed by physical occurred in 128 women (39.6%) and finally sexual violence (rape) which occurred in 48 women (14.9%). Simple assault (slapping or hitting) was the major form of physical violence by husband occurred in 85 cases (66.4%).

Conclusions: About half of women were victims of DV in this study. Psychological violence was the major form. Some women were at higher risks for DV by husband. Reliable and accurate data regarding violence against women are still limited and information about different incidents of violence against women is still confidential and not reported to governmental institutions or agencies especially in this country. For this reason, further sophisticated studies about this subject are recommended.

Introduction: Violence is an important public health problem world wide. Despite the prevalence of male victimization, women are overrepresented in virtually all forms of research on victimization. Women violence perpetrated within relationships that are supposed to involve care and protection is a much more serious

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problem than violence perpetrated by strangers [1].

In one study about (29%) of women and about (22%) of men had experienced sort of physical, sexual, or psychological intimate partner violence during their life time[2].**The aim of this study** is to assess the prevalence and type of violence against women, and studying possible risk factors that may be associated with this.

Patients and methods: From March 2006 to August 2006, a convenient sample(WHO sampling method)[3] of 323 Arabian women (265 married, 34 widows, 24 divorced) were observed at Al-Kadhimiya and Al-Kindy teaching hospitals and interviewed to determine their exposure to violence. Their age ranged from 18 to 70 years (Mean age 39 years).They were interviewed regardless whether they were attending as a patients or not. The data was gathered using a questionnaire form constructed by the researcher, including past or present history of experiencing violence by husband and or family, type of violence, with some female criteria. Mentally retarded were excluded.

Results: Domestic violence (DV) by husband was reported in 186 women (57.6%) for at least for one incident, continuous or current violence occurred in 117 women (44%).Violence not by husband was reported in 67 women (20.7%) including 16 women (5%) with continued exposure to violence. Psychological violence was the major type of DV by husband occurring in185 women (57.3%), followed by physical occurred in 128 women (39.6%) and finally sexual violence (rape) which occurred in 48 women (14.9%).

Psychological violence by husband significantly led to physical violence (P<0.05) in 127 cases of violence (68.6%) and the last significantly led to sexual violence (P<0.05) in 44 cases of violence (34.4%). About (2.5%) of women of study group had family history of 1st or 2nd degree relative who was murdered by her husband, and (2.8%) had family history of a relative (women) who were killed or kidnapped not by husband. Police report took place only in 12 cases (9.1%) for DV by husband while no police report recorded for violence not by husband. Table (1) shows the distribution of violence, types of violence, murdered females, and police report against offender(s)

Table (1): Distribution of violence, types of violence, murdered females, and police report against offender(s)

Violence against women	Violence by husband	Violence not by husband
Violence at least for one time	186(57.6%)	67(20.7%)
Current violence	117(44%)	16(5.0%)
Violence types		
Psychological violence	185(57.3%)	66(20.4%)
Physical violence	128(39.6%)	29(9.0%)
Sexual violence	48(14.9%)	3(0.9%)
Police report against the offender(s)	12(9.1%)	0
Relative murdered or kidnapped	8(2.5%)	9(2.8%)

Simple assault (slapping or hitting) was the major form of physical violence by husband occurred in 85 cases (66.4%).Aggravated assault (using knife or gun) occurred in 5 cases (3.9%). DV by husband was associated with bruises

in 61 cases (47.7%), permanent deformity in 14 cases (10.9%), and psychological disturbances like anxiety, low self esteem, depression, and suicide in 132 cases (71.9%). Other forms of violence include son preference occurred in 57 cases (18.1%) and work harassment occurred in 9 cases (14.8%). Table (2) shows the distribution of sub-types of violence.

Table (2) shows the distribution of sub-types of violence.

Psychological violence	Violence by husband	Violence not by husband
Call by names	21(11.3 %)	7(10.6%)
Humiliation	33(17.7%)	21(31.8%)
All types	132(71%)	38(57.6%)
Total	186	66
Physical violence		
Slapping/ hitting	85(66.4%)	27(93.1%)
Kicking by foot	2(1.6%)	0
Using object	2(1.6%)	0
All types	34(26.6%)	2(6.9%)
Using knife/ gun	5(3.9%)	0
Total	128	29
Sexual violence		
Rape	48(14.9%)	0
Sexual assault	0	3(0.9%)

By studying female's criteria of those women experienced DV by husband. Violence by husband occurred in all 24 divorced women during the period of their marriage making (100%). Violence also occurred in (90%) of the 41 women got married with out their agreement, and in (90.5%) of the 21 women whose husbands are married to more than one wife. For years of formal education for woman highest violence rate was

(75.3%) for (0 - 4) years, and in the presence of son preference the rate was (73.7%) or 42 case from 57 women with history of son preference, and all above were significantly associated with DV by husband ($P < 0.05$). Other factors that may be associated with DV by husband include the following where violence rate was, (59%) in not working women, (62.7%) in history of former violence by family and or relatives and (69.2%) for age of women at marriage at (10 -14) years. For male(husband) significant risk factors for perpetrator include, alcohol intake (79.5%), illegal relationships (95%), and years of formal education for husband (71.8%) for (0 - 4) years (for all $P < 0.05$). Other factors that may be associated, but not significantly, with perpetration in male include, not working man (88.8%), drug addiction (100%), and later age at marriage (65.2%) for (>38 years) at marriage. Also there are some factors that may be associated with DV against women include residence (61.9%) for rural, income (62%) for not enough income, home ownership (65.6%) for nor own nor rent house. Table (3) summarizes some female factors associated with violence.

Table (4) shows the relation between years of formal education for women and husbands / Age at marriage for women & husbands and violence. Table (5) summarizes some male and other factors associated with violence against women.

It is interesting to know that (33.4%) of women accept DV by men, and (23.5%) believe that woman should not argue man in discussion, beside (38.4%) think that man is better than woman.

Table(3)	Violence within marriage				Total		X²	P-value
Current marital status	yes	%	no	%	No.	%	19.371	0.000
Married	145	54.7	120	45.3	265	100		
Widow	17	50	17	50	34	100		
Divorced	24	100	0	0	24	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Occupation of women								
Employee or free job	45	53.6	39	46.4	84	100	0.749	0.387
Housewife	141	59	98	41	239	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Married by agreement								
By agreement	149	52.8	133	47.2	282	100	20.507	0.000
No agreement	37	90	4	9.8	41	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Multiple wives for husband								
Present other wife	19	90.5	2	9.5	21	100	9.948	0.002
No other wife	167	55.3	135	44.7	302	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Son preference								
Son preference	42	73.7	15	26.3	57	100	7.494	0.006
No preference	139	53.9	119	46.1	258	100		
Total	181	57.5	134	42.5	315	100		
Former violence not by husband								
Former violence	42	62.7	25	37.3	67	100	0.901	0.343
No former violence	144	56.3	112	43.8	256	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		

Table 4	Violence within marriage				Total		X²	P-value
Years of formal education for women	yes	%	no	%	No.	%	16.365	0.001
0 - 4	67	75.3	22	24.7	89	100		
5 - 9	65	53.3	57	46.7	122	100		
10 - 14	38	48.1	41	51.9	79	100		
> 15	16	48.5	17	51.5	33	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Age of women at marriage								
10 - 14	27	69.2	12	30.8	39	100	6.615	0.158
15 - 19	72	61	46	39	118	100		
20 - 24	45	50	45	50	90	100		
25 - 29	27	61.4	17	38.6	44	100		
> 30	15	46.9	17	53.1	32	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Years of formal education for husbands								
0 - 4	28	71.8	11	28.2	39	100	8.015	0.046
5 - 9	86	61.9	53	38.1	139	100		
10 - 14	46	50	46	50	92	100		
> 15	26	49.1	27	50.9	53	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Age of husbands at marriage								
14 - 19	22	59.5	15	40.5	37	100	2.066	0.724
20 - 25	49	52.7	44	47.3	93	100		
26 - 31	76	60.3	50	39.7	126	100		
32 - 37	24	54.5	20	45.5	44	100		
>38	15	65.2	8	34.8	23	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		

Table (5) summarizes some male and other factors associated with violence women.

Occupation of husband	Violence within marriage				Total		X ²	P-value
	yes	%	no	%	No.	%		
Employee	67	58.3	48	41.7	115	100	3.446	0.179
Free job	105	55.3	85	44.7	190	100		
Not working	14	88.8	4	22.2	18	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Alcohol intake for husband								
Drink alcohol	31	79.5	8	20.5	39	100	8.711	0.003
Not alcoholic	155	54.6	129	45.4	284	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Drug addiction for husband								
Drug addict	3	100	0	0	3	100	2.230	0.135
Not addicted	183	57.2	137	42.8	320	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Illegal relationship for husband								
Illegal relationship	19	95	1	5	20	100	12.219	0.000
No relation	167	55.1	136	44.9	303	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Husband relative to his wife or not								
Foreigner	87	58	63	42	150	100	0.118	0.943
2nd degree relative	66	56.4	51	43.6	117	100		
3rd degree relative	33	58.9	23	41.1	56	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Residence								
Urban	173	57.3	129	42.7	302	100	0.172	0.679
Rural	13	61.9	8	38.1	21	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Income								
Not enough	57	62	35	38	92	100	1.006	0.316
Enough for living/ saving	129	55.8	102	44.2	231	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		
Home ownership								
Own	104	57.5	77	42.5	181	100	2.685	0.261
Rent	42	51.9	39	48.1	81	100		
Neither own nor rent	40	65.6	21	34.4	61	100		
Total	186	57.6	137	42.4	323	100		

Discussion: These results showed that high proportions of women are victims of any sort of violence whether psychological, physical, and or sexual from their husbands and experiencing psychological violence alone is not a simple problem because it may leads to amore sever form of violence. Lower rate of report make it difficult for researchers to investigate the problem or to collect data from governmental

agencies and or police stations. The effects of violence are very important thing as they may interfere with women's life and performance. Women's ideas and believes regarding marital relationship and women's rights should be improved in the way that every one in this relationship has rights and obligations.

Certain groups of women are at higher rate of risk of being abused by their husbands include those who are not working, low educated women, married

without agreement, presence of other wife, former history of violence and son preference by parents of women.

Results of this study are to some what similar to results of researches done in Arabic areas [4] where 52% of Palestinians women showed that they had been experienced physical violence at least one time for the year 2000 and in study done in Jordan showed that percent of women who were continuously being physically abused by their husbands was 47.6%. But there is a little difference from studies done nation wide. The reason may be the socio-demographic features in common for Arabic countries. Some forms of violence were prevalent in this study while other forms were absent like female circumcision.

Some factors might have contributed in prevailing violence in this country including successive wars, deterioration of security situation, unemployment, and psychological traumas contributed to frustration which may be expressed as verbal or physical violence. Absence of reliable data regarding these incidents of violence has faced us with difficulties in doing a research regard this subject, therefore; we depended this type of study for our research which may not reflect the true prevalence of violence in this country.

Conclusions: About half of women were victims of DV in this study. Psychological violence was the major form. Some women were at higher

risks for DV by husband. Reliable and accurate data regarding violence against women are still limited and information about different incidents of violence against women is still confidential and not reported to governmental institutions or agencies especially in this country. For this reason, further sophisticated studies about this subject are recommended.

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